

ISSUES OF POPULARIZATION OF ADDITIONAL TYPES OF SERVICES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE COMMUNICATIVE ENVIRONMENT IN MUSEUMS OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: The development of museum communication, the expansion of viewer visits, on the basis of which increasing its income are considered the basis of museum tourism. According to its communicative function, museums are not only historically significant, but also serve the active participation of modern man in socio-cultural processes, ensuring harmony with society. Expanding the range of activities of modern museums in Uzbekistan will increase the demand for cultural tourism resources and expand the employment of not only museum staff, but also art managers, designers, artists, art critics.

Keywords: services provided by the museum auditorium, theatrical programs, additional types of services, museum stores, museum circles, cultural and educational events, exhibitions.

Introduction. The fact that in the context of current globalization, the preservation and display of museum objects become one of the important tasks means that each people has a deeper understanding of their history and culture. Strengthening their material technical base in the activities of museums in this regard is one of the main pressing issues. Therefore, it is important to develop a targeted plan for the construction, reconstruction, repair and equipping of state-owned museum buildings in 2023-2026 with modern technologies and improving exposure and fund conditions. In order to ensure the implementation of the tasks set out in the "addressed plan" of additional services to be established in state museums in 2022-2023, the activities of "Museum shop" approved by the application of the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan PD-261 dated May 27, 2022 on measures to develop the service sector in museums [1].

Research methodology. Mainly the scientific sources of foreign researchers were studied on the topic. In the researches of P.Michael, M.Brayden and J. Hall, for the first time, special attention was paid to the development of projects related to the tourism economy in European states, recommendations on free tourists, the establishment of a marketing system in museum tourism [12,46]. It mainly focuses on the long years of observations of the authors in the field of tourism, the development of the trade of souvenirs in museum tourism on the basis of their practical experience.

The description of large-scale work in the field of museum tourism, planning, marketing and management of this area and the study of regional characteristics, forms of work with spectators, specific aspects of the development of innovative tourism was considered on the basis of studies dedicated to the work experience of European museums [9, 82]. It was the scope of these studies that served as an important resource in the study of the prospects for the implementation of foreign experiments on the development of the activities of museums in the Cultural Tourism of Uzbekistan. The authors cited some statistical and factual information regarding the adaptation to tourism, the practice of museum tourism, on the basis of conservation of museum objects.

In the development of cultural tourism, the creation of curatorial projects, the study of museum communiqué, the organization of museum-show festivals in the system of ethnographic and art museums, management and practical developments in the financial development of museum store activities were analyzed in the scope of dissertations carried out in research centers such as the United States, England, France[20, 32]. In the first half of the 21st century, modern activities for the development of museum tourism, innovative solutions have been studied on the basis of the work experience of Museums of various specialties.

And from the Uzbek-language sources, the importance of museum shops in the development of cultural tourism is based in M. Mukhamedova's graduation work "Museum auctions"[13,20]. Also, Sh. Kasimova's article also cites processes related to the activities of museum souvenirs [11, 14].

In order to develop an innovative and practical mechanism for the development of museums, improving the quality of provided services and infrastructure, strengthen the country's prestige in the field of World Culture, the decision of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan on August 26, 2018 PR-3920 "on measures for the innovative development of culture and art in the Republic of Uzbekistan", Resolution PR-4068 of December 19, 2018 "on measures to radically improve activities in the field of protection of objects of material cultural heritage", resolution 1019 "on approval of the program for improving the activities of museums in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2020-2021" of December 19, 2019, resolution 1019 "on measures to further increase the role and impact of the sphere of Culture and art in the life of society", dated May 26, 2020 PD – serves to some extent in the study of these processes in the implementation of the tasks established by Decree No. 6000 and other adopted regulatory legal acts related to this activity.

Results and Discussions. Analyzing the museum management and marketing system to determine how productive it is, comparing its results, that is, the requirements of customers and the proposals of the museum's types of services, the necessary modifications are made to further increase the productivity of this system if necessary. In order to study the requirements and wishes of customers and to find out their opinion, it will be necessary to enter a book of proposals and questionnaires. In surveys, it is necessary to enter a system of points indicating the quality level of museum services. In this direction, it is also important for the museum staff to study how the work in the field of supply and demand in the experienced museums of the Republic is organized. Sharing mutual experience is also not without benefit if necessary. Having received the information obtained as a result of the analysis, creating new programs on the fronts that the museum management and marketing could not cover, the client is divided into information about what he wants, what kind of brand will be a well purchased. In this regard, the museum can draw up separate questionnaires for different classes of customers (children, adults, local residents, guests, foreign guests) and give the intended result of distribution. When the filled-in questionnaires are analyzed and an idea of the demand and need of the market is formed, a lot of attention is paid to these conclusions in the activities of the museum. It should be noted that the opinions of a particular group do not correspond to the opinions of a second group. Some visitors can find auxiliary entries in the exposition (text, Label, Graphics, charts, etc.), and while “the viewer” demands that without an excavator, there are more explanatory texts to understand the meaning of the exposition, to produce imagination“, another group of opinions also expressed the opinion that historical objects should stand in the exposition, no distracting papers are needed. It is significant that auxiliary texts are used in moderation to eliminate this controversy. When later distributed surveys were analyzed, it became clear that most customers expressed a desire to see live history. In general, museum marketing is a type of service that studies the thought desires, suggestions of the audience coming to the museum. The better the museum marketing is put on the trail, the greater the visit of the museum's audience.

Although the concept of marketing, which is developing in museology, is being used in museums of our country from the very beginning, there will be no exaggeration if we say much better that the situations that are being implemented in our museums. In particular, the new projects “Culture of the Republic of Korea”, “exposition of the children's museum”, organized at the State Museum of the

history of Uzbekistan, are one of the new directions in the study of marketing directions developing in Uzbekistan. Because, the renewal of museum expositions sets the stage for an increase in the audience, the development of museum pedagogy.

In addition, the “tropical butterfly exhibition” of Russia, held at the Museum of Art of Uzbekistan, gives viewers the opportunity to learn about tropical nature and a branch of the living animal world, and this unconventional exhibition has aroused great interest and admiration in viewers. The exhibition is intended to be held from February 15 to April 21, 2013, reflecting interstate cooperation and creating an inter-museum experience exchange. The exhibition “children's creativity”, held in the State Museum of the history of Uzbekistan, was held in October 2012 at the State Museum of the history of the Timurids in order to study the history of the foreign countries and their culture more widely and develop Museum pedagogy among schoolchildren, “do you know Belgium?”, a photo exhibition and a screening contest on “my impressions from the museum” were organized. About 60 photographs of famous Belgian architectural examples, art, science were put on display, as well as a film about Belgium. In the main texts of the exhibition, information about the history of Belgium, Public Administration, politics, culture was given in Uzbek, Russian, English, and the labels of the photos selected for the exhibition were presented in three languages in order to be accessible to visitors.

Organized exhibitions aimed to increase the love of schoolchildren for history, for the museum, enrich the spirituality of our youth, to form a culture of spectacle in them. In addition, young families who are stepping into a new life visit the Museum, get acquainted with the history, culture, art of the Timurid's period, which is considered the most fruitful period of Uzbekistan's history, get acquainted with it more widely, and fall into the pictures for memorabilia. These factors that are causing the development of Museum marketing will not be an exaggeration if we say the first steps taken in the marketing of Uzbek museum studies.

“Permanent” or “temporary” expositions organized in the shell of the museum building are considered traditional types of expositions. They choose the idea that the main goal is promoted based on the wishes of today's audience and the requirements of the period. An interesting display of exhibits, in which traces of different eras, history and societies are sealed, has a huge capacity of intellectual and emotional impact. The museum can witness the clash of eras, societies, thoughts and ideas. It is appropriate to mark the attention of developed

countries to museums, especially museums of artistic orientation, precisely by the role of the museum as a repository of large spiritual nutrients. It is possible to observe a professional approach to art museums and expositions in countries where the role of art or artistic creation as a model of spiritual thinking is stabilized, serving to satisfy the spiritual needs of the new generation.

Today in world practice, great attention is paid to the exposition and exhibition projects organized in museums. The exposition, which is special in the scientific, practical, creative work of museum employees, acts as a bridge of communication between the era and the viewer, or between the creator and the viewer, creating an interaction with history and time. As a result of great creative work, the exposition becomes a tool that serves to increase the artistic taste, intellectual potential and knowledge of young people. Expositions made up of masterpieces of world and domestic art can bring aesthetic pleasure to the soul of any individual viewer. There is no doubt that works of art that are special in the human hand and intellects are not only a beautiful object suitable for the human eye, but also a factor that affects its psyche, inner voice. For this reason, the exposition activities in museums, the types of displays of exhibits, are naturally expanding and developing.

The museum can also host exhibits outside the shell of its building. This is mainly is connected with various projects. Traveling exhibitions are considered the widest type of show, consisting of one and more, and sometimes a group of exhibits. Traveling exhibitions may be one-time, or have become part of the state's national system. For example, the famous Swedish Exhibition “Rijskuntallningar” presents exhibitions of various sizes in the peat corners of the world. In 2006, the exhibition “Eastern dreams: Russian avant-garde and Bukharan silk (“Gryozhi o Vostoke: russkiy avangard ishelka Bukhari”), organized by The “Forum of Culture and art of Uzbekistan” Foundation in Petersburg, was a large-scale traveling exhibition project organized in the modern artistic process of Uzbekistan. The main foundation of the exhibition was created by the foundation of the Department of painting of Uzbekistan of the State Museum of Art of Uzbekistan. Naturally, this exhibition is doomed to success, because in its boldly solved concept of art studies, the traditional signs of oriental aesthetics and the Russian avant-garde were skillfully combined.

Traveling exhibitions although the most complex, requiring large funds and qualifications, is the type of exhibition, it is rewarded in return by placing the museum, exhibits of artistic, historical and other nature in it, in other countries,

in a wide public display. That is the main goal of such projects in the nature of propaganda and agitation.

Traveling exhibits include “blockbuster” [21, 48] exhibits Ham, which claim millions of dollars in vehicles, montage, and other spending. The type of blockbuster exhibition is relevant today. Because the function of an exhibit that reveals the values, history, national identity of a society, or illuminates the evolution of a certain type of objects, as item and art, is changing to this day. The expositions of Museums of the world focus on “the evolution of the exhibit – the present echo of the social environment, which is rapidly deformed in the image.” The viewer, in need of spiritual and cultural feed, has forgotten museums and galleries in many cases, seeking this need from such informative tools as television, cinema, the internet. And the blockbuster exhibition, dedicated to the project of a big idea, is a unique solution to the problem of attracting a large number of spectators to the museum [19, 55]. Although such exhibitions require a large expenditure, a specific artistic decoration, a special management approach, special arrangements for the safety and preservation of the exhibit, many major museums around the world happily accept them in their premises. “For the first time in the 1970s, “Tutankhamun” and “San Marco horse”. After such exhibitions as” Venice”, blockbuster exhibitions moving to various museums and on display have gained popularity, and today it has become a key feature of the era of globalization” [21,67]. They provide the viewer with such an invaluable opportunity to get acquainted with unique and valuable exhibits or to see the famous exhibits with a fresh look. Museum merchandising examples developed on the basis of these exhibits also play an important role in museum advertising and souvenir sales.

In order to develop additional services, clubs and theatrical performances are organized in various cultural centers and museums around the world. The Centre for Fine Arts is a multi-purpose cultural venue in the Royal Quarter of Brussels, Belgium. It is often referred to as **BOZAR** (a homophone of *Beaux-arts*) in French or by its initials **PSK** in Dutch. This multidisciplinary space was designed to bring together a wide range of artistic events, whether music, visual arts, theatre, dance, literature, cinema or architecture[22]. Tourists can discover the cultural and artistic programs by concerts, exhibitions, contemporary dance and theatre performances held in Bozar.

Bemish **Museum** is the first regional open-air museum, in England located at Beamish, near the town of Stanley, in County Durham, England is also well known as theatrical museum. Beamish pioneered the concept of a living museum.

By displaying duplicates or replaceable items, it was also an early example of the now commonplace practice of museums allowing visitors to touch objects[23]. “From music and dance to storytelling and food” is one of the theatrical exhibitions held in Bemish museum. It has recognizes as the perfect example of museum theatres.

This experience was carried out in a number of Museums of our republic. In particular, in the State Museum of the history of Applied Arts and crafts of Uzbekistan for 2017-2018, master classes and an exhibition-fair for local and foreign visitors with the participation of craftsmen in such directions as embroidery, pottery, carpet weaving, wood carving were organized permanently. In order to widely promote not only our material but also intangible cultural heritage, a creative group demonstrating folklore communities, national songs and songs, folk games and customs was formed, and daily cultural events were regularly organized for visitors.

Due to the lack of financial resources in its turn to continue this project, the activities of folkloric communities have ceased.

In order to promote our traditions, folklore and national dishes in the major museums of our republic, especially on the beaches visited from abroad, the following:

- It will be advisable to organize a demonstration of theatrical performances in the Regional Museum of local lore “Ark” within the Bukhara State Museum Reserve, in the Museum of Applied decorative art of Mokhi-Khossa. In the Khan Reception Room of the Regional Museum of local lore” Ark”, It is possible to stage the broadcasting processes of Amir Said Olimkhan by reading the decree of the ambassador of Iran, India, Tsarist Russia, Khiva Khanate, Kokand Khanate or Amir Said Olimkhan. It is also possible to stage the reception of ambassadors, meetings on various topics, folklore and other processes in the Museum of Applied decorative art of Mokhi-Hossa;

- In the courtyard of the Kohna Ark in the State Museum-Reserve” Ichan-Kala”, that is, in the viewing room, it is possible to perform performances staged under the music of the Khan's performance “the song of the Khan”, while performing such stage performances as receiving ambassadors from Iran, Tsarist Russia, the emirate of Bukhara, the Kokand Khanate, reading the Khan's decree;

- In the Local History Museum in the Samarkand State Museum-Reserve, it is possible to stage a meeting of members of the Merchant Guild (merchant nobility). It is also possible to conduct stage performances in the Registan complex by the

Directorate of repair and use of the Registan ensemble, such as the proclamation of the decree of the people's holiday, the ruler;

In the Kokand state museum-reserve, the palace of Khudoyarkhan can display the stage performances of the embassies, poets and music masters dating back to the reign of Khudoyar Khan and Umar Khan.

At one time, the museum was considered a simple and clear structure. Its state schedule consisted of a director, guards, and observers in halls. But the times have changed, completely new employees have appeared in museums: accountants, engineers, secretaries, museum educators, specialists in repair, advertising and public relations, etc. In other words, the museum has become a normal bureaucratic organization with established procedures, a standard schedule of positions and tasks[4,3]. Based on the demand of the times, there is a need to add a marketer, SMM manager and other state units to develop museums commercial activities. For large museums in our country, namely museums and reserves, it is advisable to carry out projects of a live museum (theatrical performances) for a foreign audience.

To organize these theatrical performances in the museum-reserves, it is necessary to change and add to the paragraph II Chapter (Museum-reserves) of the annex part of the order of the Minister of Tourism and sports “on approval of the model states of state museums, Museum-reserves, house-museums” of October 25, 2021.

It is advisable to add to the current sample State table of the museum-reserves –the following State amount[2]. By making changes to the schedule of this state, it is achieved to promote the customs, art, culture of our country to our people, and, moreover, to a foreign audience. Alternatively, the ground is laid for improving the financial resource of museums through the growth of visitors to museums and the sale of kitchens, art shops organized in museums.

At the moment, state museums in the Republic provide paid service from activities such as ticket sales, excursion service, the use of photo and video service in the museum building and its territory, and the rental of vacant spaces, for a total of about 25.6 million in 2023. The sum was earned. At the moment, even if the law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 732 of November 26, 2021 permits the conduct of commercial activities in museums, regulatory documents on the conduct of commercial activities of museums (paid service) and its regulation have not been adopted by ministries and departments.

As a result, museums only carry out work to sell tickets to visitors, photograph the objects in the museum exposition (amateur photo), and lower

money into the museum's out-of-budget funds by renting out buildings and facilities.

In the event that, on the basis of the order of the head of the museum, the regulation on the conduct of commercial activities and the prices attached to it (price current) are approved, various objections are encountered by individuals and legal entities, including situations when the price is fixed based on which norms.

As a solution to this problem, it is necessary to develop a draft regulation on the establishment of the procedure for paid service in state museums by the higher standing body of museums, agree with ministries and departments in the established procedure and approve it.

The following should be taken into account in the formation of types of paid service activities corresponding to the goals of the organization of museums in this regulation:

Types of paid services for visitors in museums:

- Ticket sales;
- Conducting an excursion;
- Animals: horse, pony, camel, as well as conducting an excursion using special electric vehicle vehicles;
- Holding lectures;
- Conducting master classes;
- Holding circles (in crafts, fine arts and other directions).

Services provided by museums on cultural and educational events, exhibitions:

- Organization of cultural and educational events, creative meetings;
- Allocation of temporary rooms for holding exhibitions to individuals or legal entities in the building of the museum, organizational and artistic preparation of the exhibition;
- Organization of expositions and exhibitions for other museums, cultural and educational organizations (formation of a 3D design project, concept and thematic plan of museum expositions and exhibitions, preparation of artistic decoration);
- Providing advice, methodological, creative and organizational support in conducting expositions and exhibitions of other museums and cultural and educational organizations;
- Rental of showcases, stands and other inventory on the balance sheet of the museum to individuals and legal entities for the organization of portable

exhibitions (excluding showcases, stands and other inventory standing in the exposition);

- Organization of quests on various topics;
- Organization of interactive spaces, activities and attractions for children on the territory of the museum, exposition;
- Service to guests at exhibitions, cultural and educational events, seminars and conferences organized by individuals and legal entities.

Services for trade work carried out by museums:

- Sale of polygraph and book products;
- Sale of souvenir products;
- Rental of physical and legal entities to capture old military uniforms, national and other types of uniforms in photo and video. Services provided by museum items and collections:

- Service for accounting, maintenance, scientific recommendations of museum objects and collections to other state and non-state museums;

- Restoration and restoration of museum objects and collections;

- Grant to legal entities and individuals the right to publish or publish museum objects and collections in printed, electronic and other types of media, including through virtual mode;

- Organization of a service for copying museum objects and collections in Virtual tourist programs on a paid basis with a photo and an exhibit in 3D form;

- Rent museum items and collections to local and foreign museums, organizations for temporary display at the exhibition;

- Granting by individuals and legal entities the right to the building of the museum, the object of cultural heritage within the museum, professional photo and video shooting of museum objects, shooting films on various topics and publishing them in the media, in various publications. Other types of services carried out by museums:

- Use of the museum buildings and its territory as a pavilion (professional photo and video shooting);

- Transportation and delivery service of people and related goods of buses and cargo standing on the account of museums;

- Organization of a parking service for the reception of vehicles on the territory of museums;

- Organization of rental points for sports, leisure equipment and inventory in museums;

- Providing advertising service to legal entities and individuals (excluding objects of cultural heritage), with the installation of advertising signs and LED screens on the premises of the museum and its territory.

As a result of scientific research, the price current of the above types of activities was developed[3].

Conclusion/Recommendations. The cultural heritage agency, together with the Academy of Fine Arts of Uzbekistan and the Ministry of construction, should develop a model project of art galleries. At this, a demonstration hall for expositions, youth training and creativity rooms, “master-apprentice” practice rooms, a modern library-cafe, art workshops for creative people are organized. The construction of its buildings will be carried out within the framework of a phased investment program for the period 2022-2026. The Council of Ministers of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, regions and Tashkent City Halls will ensure the allocation of land plots for the construction of galleries in accordance with the administrative regulation of the allocation of land plots for permanent use for state and public needs, approved by the decree of the Cabinet of Ministers No. 543 of August 27, 2021. In the development of project and estimate documentation, special attention is paid to the approval of the new concept of each state museum and the reliable storage of museum objects, the creation of favorable conditions for visitors, the development of the field of Service and marketing, architectural planning, interior, design and landscape solutions. In order to transport museum items without security, to create conditions for students to visit young people, at the expense of the state budget, the relevant state museums are provided with bus and cargo vehicles.

It is important that the project and estimate documentation of state museums is carried out within the framework of the annual investment programs for newly built and reconstructed objects from the economy, the state budget, which is allocated to the field of tourism and cultural heritage in the appropriate order of perfect and current repair facilities, and at the expense of local budget funds and other It is ensured that the work on the perfect and current renovation and equipment of the buildings of state museums will be envisaged annually from 2023 in the development of state budget parameters. Important processes are considered to ensure the development of real estate objects of State museum-reserves and cultural heritage of special importance at the expense of the state budget with fire safety, video surveillance devices and modern turnstile equipment and their further maintenance.

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